

Seeking Serendipity: repurposing DataCite metadata to augment ANDS discovery

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Australian National Data Service (ANDS)

- An initiative of the Australian Government being conducted as part of the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (\$A24M) and the Super Science Initiative (\$A48M)
- A collaboration between **Monash University**, the Australian National University and CSIRO
- About 50 staff, currently funded to mid 2013
- *More researchers re-using more data more often*
- *Data as a first-class object*

ANDS enables transformation of:

Data that are:

- ☐ Unmanaged
- ☐ Disconnected
- ☐ Invisible
- ☐ Single use

To Structured Collections that are:

- ☐ Managed
- ☐ Connected
- ☐ Findable
- ☐ Reusable

so that Australian researchers can easily publish, discover, access and use research data.

ANDS is helping build the ARDC:

A meeting place for researchers and data:

- The set of data collections that are shareable
- The descriptions of the collections
- The relationships between the data, the researchers, the problems, the instruments and the institutions
- The infrastructure that enables populating and exploiting the commons

ANDS Discovery

- Discovery across disciplines
- Go to where the users are
- Provide context (discovery, assessment)
- Link to discipline portals
- Provide window into ARDC

‘See Also’

- Provide suggested links based on range of criteria
- Supports serendipity
- Gradually adding functionality

Stage 1 – Internal suggestions

- [Demo](#)

Stage 2 – draw on DataCite

- Enabled by availability of DataCite Search API
- Use existing RDA title as search probe against DataCite metadata
- Search in real time, add results to suggested links
- Aim for best possible match first, but reduce match percentage if no results returned
- Rank dataset results ahead of other resourceTypes
- [Demo](#)

Stage 3 – TBD

- National Library of Australia?
- Australian Spatial Data Directory?
- Atlas of Living Australia?
- NARCIS?

Possible enhancements

- Tweak search ranking at DataCite end to highlight what ANDS cares about?
- ‘See Also’ at search level (not just record level)?
- Use path followed to get to current page to rerank terms in search query
- Use RDA Subject description to provide richer search request

Structuring serendipity: expanding See Also

- “Same” or “similar” spatial coverage
- “Same” or “similar” temporal coverage
- If related info contains publications and information on the authors of the publication: collections linked to co-authors
- Shared keywords and descriptions

Issues for future

- Does DataCite care that View Resolve Record involves a traffic bypass?
- How will this approach scale to lots of ‘see also’ sources?
 - performance scaling
 - UI scaling
- Who cares - richness vs. complexity tradeoffs

Questions?

- ands.org.au
- researchdata.ands.org.au
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- andrew.treloar.net
- <http://www.slideshare.net/atreloar/seeking-serendipity>

RESEARCH DATA AUSTRALIA

SEARCH

Advanced Search

Research Data Australia is a discovery service for Australian research data.

What's in Research Data Australia

Research datasets or collections of research materials.

COLLECTIONS

[Browse All Collections \(39,339\)](#)

Researchers or research organisations that create or maintain research datasets or collections.

PARTIES

[Browse All Parties \(5,257\)](#)

Services that support the creation or use of research datasets or collections.

SERVICES

[Browse All Services \(78\)](#)

Projects or programs that create research datasets or collections.

ACTIVITIES

[Browse All Activities \(27,408\)](#)

Spotlight on research domains

More information on research data infrastructure for specific domains:

NCRIS and EIF Capability - Integrated Marine Observing System

Integrated Marine Observing System (IMOS) has deployed observing equipment in the oceans around Australia, with data freely and openly available through the IMOS Ocean Portal.

<http://www.imos.org.au/>

Institutionally Managed

Externally Managed

